

Enhancement of mechanical, electrical and dielectric properties in poly(vinylidene fluoride) composites with two dimensional nanomaterials

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Development of a new generation polymer nanocomposites have been explored using poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) with functionalized two dimensional (2D) nanomaterials. We have functionalized graphene oxide (GO) by imidazolium based ionic liquid, polyaniline, polythiophene-*g*-poly(methyl methacrylate) and prepared their nanocomposite with PVDF. We have also functionalized exfoliated molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) by polyaniline and prepared composites with PVDF. The morphology and physical properties of all the composites are described. All the prepared functionalized 2D materials shows synergistic effect on the enhancement of piezoelectric beta polymorph and also improve the dielectric properties of PVDF enormously.

Keywords: Ionic liquid, polyaniline, molybdenum disulfide, beta polymorph, dielectric constant.

Introduction

Two dimensional (2D) nanomaterials having large surface area with very low thickness had initiated emerging research interest over the past decade because of their exciting thermal, mechanical, optoelectronic properties¹. One of the intensively studied 2D nanomaterial is graphene since its discovery in 2004². It has one atom thick planar structure containing sp²-hybridized carbon atoms and has large surface area (2600 m²/g), excellent thermal, mechanical, and electrical properties³. Another 2D nanomaterial that has shown immense attention at present is molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) which has typical layered structure where S-Mo-S layers are held together by van der Waals forces⁴. It shows unique electrical, mechanical, photonic and catalytic properties^{4,5}.

In recent years, polymer nanocomposites with two dimensional nanomaterials have enjoyed significant attention because of their greatly extended applications in different fields⁶. They often show various important mechanical, photocatalytic, optoelectronic, dielectric properties compare to the bulk polymer matrix⁷. Different physical properties of polymer nanocomposites mainly depend on the aspect ratio, interfacial interaction as well as dispersion quality of nanofillers in

the polymer matrix. Simple physical mixing of these nanofillers in polymer matrix often causes agglomeration because of the lack of the interfacial incompatibility^{6,7}. To overcome these problems, surface functionalization of the nanomaterials is the most effective strategy. Surface functionalized nanomaterials may be made with some special small molecules or polymers that also helps nanomaterials to be compatible with the bulk polymer. Ionic liquids, consisting of imidazolium cations with some counter anions are interesting compounds considered as "green solvents" having high thermal stability, high ionic conductivity, low flammability. They are used in many electrochemical and nanotechnological applications⁸. Many ionic liquids have functional behavior which can be used as multifunctional materials. Polyaniline is one of the most important conducting polymers having reversible redox behavior, good electrical conductivity and high dielectric constant and hence it find uses in chemical sensors, dielectric materials etc.^{9,10}.

Among other polymers poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is very attractive polymer because of its extraordinary pyro-, piezoelectric properties which makes it technologically important to build sensors and actuators. It has four commonly known crystalline forms e.g. α , β , γ , δ phases depending

upon the stereochemical structures with alternating *gauche* and *trans* C-C bonds. β -phase PVDF is amongst the most important because of their superior piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties¹¹. β -phase of PVDF film can be produced by incorporating varieties of fillers, like hydrated ionic salt, clay, BaTiO₃, PMMA, CNTs, Pd, Au, Ag etc.^{12,13}. Although these methods are suitable for producing the polar β -phase PVDF, they are not superior compared to the reinforcement property of the nanomaterials. To obtain higher amount of beta phase PVDF there also need strong interaction between the nanofiller surface with the >CF₂ dipoles of PVDF. Again there are common methods to improve the dielectric constant of PVDF by dispersing high dielectric constant perovskite-like ceramic materials. But to get high dielectric value the amount of fillers needs to be high that lowers flexibility of the nanocomposite films¹⁴.

Here we present different functionalization methods (covalent and noncovalent) of graphene oxide (GO) and molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) by ionic liquid, polythiophene, and polyaniline (PANI). Incorporation of these functionalized nanomaterials into PVDF produces nanocomposites where the nanofillers are well dispersed into the PVDF matrix. In each case we have obtained significantly higher amount of β -phase compare to pure PVDF and in case of the composite with polyaniline functionalized GO it exhibits the highest content of 91%. Improvement of mechanical properties are observed by the incorporation of ionic liquid functionalized graphene (GO-IL) and polythiophene-graft-poly(methyl methacrylate) functionalized graphene (PT-g-PMMA). Significant improvement of dielectric properties also have been shown in all the nanocomposites and MoS₂-PANI/PVDF film has shown maximum dielectric constant of 586 at 100 Hz frequency.

Experimental

Synthesis of graphene oxide (GO):

GO was prepared following Hummers' method. Graphite (1 g) was added in 25 mL concentrated H₂SO₄. NaNO₃ (500 mg) was added and was stirred for 3 h. The temperature was kept below 5°C within an ice bath and 4 g of KMnO₄ was added into the mixture together with 100 mL double distilled water. Then, 150 mL of double distilled water and 10 mL of 30% H₂O₂ were added into the mixture to stop the reaction.

The solution was then centrifuged and was washed until it reached the neutral pH. Finally, the product was dried in vacuum oven at 60°C to obtain the GO.

Synthesis of the amine-terminated ionic liquid (IL-NH₂):

5 g, 0.0609 mol of 1-methylimidazole and 12.5 g, 0.061 mol of 2-bromoethylamine hydro bromide were added in a two-necked round bottom flask, containing 75 mL of dry ethanol and was refluxed in nitrogen atmosphere for 24 h. The mixture was purified by ethyl acetate, dried and was washed with distilled ethanol. Finally it was dried under vacuum at 60°C to get IL-NH₂. To get free amine from the corresponding hydrobromide salt we added distilled methanol (50 mL) and sodium methoxide. The mixture was stirred for 1 h under N₂ atmosphere and the methanol was evaporated to get the free amine ionic liquid.

Preparation of ionic liquid functionalized graphene oxide (GO-IL):

GO-IL was synthesized by the reaction of -COOH groups of GO with -NH₂ group of IL-NH₂. In a round bottom flask, a dispersed solution of 500 mg GO, IL-NH₂ (2 ml), N,N'-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) (1 g) and 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) (500 mg) were taken in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and the mixture was stirred at 50°C for 24 h at room temperature. It was diluted with 50 mL double distilled water, while stirring slowly. The resulting mixture was washed with ethanol and dichloro methane (DCM) and the solution was centrifuged by washing with water. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and then dried to get the GO-IL.

Synthesis of polythiophene-graft-poly(methyl methacrylate) (PT-g-PMMA):

PT-g-PMMA graft copolymer was synthesized as reported in our previous work¹⁵.

Preparation of reduced graphene oxide (RGO):

500 mg of GO was taken in a 500 mL RB and 200 ml of water was added and was sonicated for 2 h. 5 mL of hydrazine monohydrate was then added and was placed in an oil bath for reflux at 100°C under stirring condition for 24 h. The color of the reaction mixture gradually changed from yellowish-brown to black. The black reduced graphene oxide (RGO) was separated and was washed by water and then with

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methanol. The resulting product was dried to get RGO.

Functionalization of RGO with PT-g-PMMA (PFG):

RGO (20 mg) was dispersed in 10 ml DMF by sonication and was kept under magnetic stirring for 2 h. 80 mg of PT-g-PMMA was added and was sonicated followed by magnetically stirring to form a homogeneous PT-g-PMMA/RGO (PFG) dispersion. The solution was centrifuged and was washed with DMF. The black color material was dried under vacuum to get PFG material.

Synthesis of amine functionalized GO (G-NH₂):

500 mg GO was taken in a RB with catalytic amount of DMF and 100 ml SOCl₂ were taken and were kept in a reflux condition at 80°C for 24 h under inert atmosphere. Excess of SOCl₂ was removed by distillation and product was re-dispersed in 40 ml dry DMF and was stirred. Then 500 mg of *p*-phenylenediamine was added to this dispersion and the reaction was continued for 3 days at 120°C under inert condition. The mixture was centrifuged by washing with DMF, distilled water and methanol, respectively. The final product was dried under vacuum oven.

Synthesis of PANI from G-NH₂ (G-g-PANI):

G-NH₂ (100 mg) was dispersed in 50 ml of distilled water and ultrasonicated for 30 min. 80 ml of 1 (M) *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (PTSA 13.776 g) was added in this dispersion and was sonicated for 30 min. This suspension was cooled to 0°C and aniline monomer (400 mL) was added to the G-NH₂ suspension with continuous stirring. A freshly prepared solution of 1.369 g of ammonium persulfate in 200 ml of water was added to the mixture. This stirring was continued for 10 h and the cooling condition was maintained. The resulting dark green material was filtered, washed several times by water, methanol and acetone followed by vacuum drying.

Synthesis of exfoliated MoS₂ (E-MoS₂):

1.5 g of bulk MoS₂ was taken with 500 mL of DMF and was sonicated for 35 h at room temperature. The dispersed solution was allowed to stand for 4 h and then the supernatant dispersed part was centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 min. This supernatant dispersion was evaporated to get exfoliated MoS₂ (E-MoS₂).

Synthesis of PANI functionalized MoS₂ (MoS₂-PANI):

100 mg of E-MoS₂ was dispersed in a flask with 100 ml of distilled water and 20 ml methanol. The flask was ultrasonicated for about 60 min. 70 mL of 1 (M) hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added and was then sonicated for 30 min. This suspension was then cooled in an ice bath at 10°C. Then aniline monomer (400 ml) was added to E-MoS₂ with continuous stirring. A freshly prepared ammonium persulfate (1.369 g in 20 ml of water) solution was slowly added to the mixture and was stirred at the cold conditions for 24 h. The resulting material was filtered and the residue was washed by water and methanol respectively followed by vacuum drying.

All the above functionalization procedures of 2D nanomaterials are summarized in Fig. 1.

Preparation of PVDF/GO-IL (GLF), PVDF/PFG (RPF), PVDF/G-g-PANI (GPF), MoS₂-PANI/PVDF (MPF) composite films:

A stock solution of each filler was prepared by dispersing 500 mg in 500 mL DMF. By mixing definite amount of the individual stock solution with 500 mg PVDF (in DMF) GLFx, RPFx, GPFx, MPFx films were prepared where x = 3, 5, 10 indicating the weight percent of the filler in the respective composites.

Characterization:

The techniques of all instrumental characterizations used here are presented in Table 1.

Results and discussion

Morphology:

Dispersion quality of the functionalized 2D nanomaterials in PVDF matrix are shown in TEM images (Fig. 2). Fig. 2a shows a homogeneous dispersion of ionic liquid functionalized GO with its sheet like structure in the bulk PVDF matrix for the GLF3 nanocomposite. Such type of homogeneous dispersion is also present in case of RPF3 (Fig. 2b) and GPF5 (Fig. 2c). The black edges of functionalized graphene sheets clearly reveal high density of graphene in the PVDF matrix. TEM image of MPF10 also supports homogeneous dispersion of polyaniline functionalized MoS₂ in PVDF implying

Fig. 1. Schematic presentation of different synthesis procedures of forming functionalized 2D nanomaterials.

strong interaction of functionalized MoS₂ with the bulk PVDF matrix (Fig. 2d).

Crystallization behaviour:

To find the crystal phases of PVDF and in the nanocomposites, FTIR spectra of all the samples are shown in Fig. 3a. Pure PVDF have the IR stretching peaks at 532, 615, 764, 796, 976 and 1385 cm⁻¹ which are characteristics of α-phase PVDF⁹. With increasing amount of G-g-PANI in PVDF the α-phase peak intensities decreases with a concomitant increase of β-phase peaks (445, 510, 840, 1275 cm⁻¹). Amount of the β-phase present in the composites are calculated from FTIR spectra by using the following eq. (1):

$$F(\beta) = \frac{X_{\beta}}{X_{\alpha} + X_{\beta}} = \frac{A_{\beta}}{(K_{\beta}/k_{\alpha}) A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta}} = \frac{A_{\beta}}{(1.26) A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta}} \quad (1)$$

In the above equation X_α and X_β denote crystalline mass fractions of α- and β-phases respectively, A_α and A_β indicate the absorbance intensities of vibration peaks at 764 and 840 cm⁻¹. K_α and K_β corresponds to the absorption coefficients 6.1×10⁴ and 7.7×10⁴ cm²/mole, respectively¹⁶. The amount of β-phase present in each composite is calculated

Table 1. Detailed of the instrumental characterizations

Name of analysis	Characterization
Fourier transform infrared spectra (FTIR)	FTIR spectra were measured on Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 100 at room temperature. Transmission mode was used and all spectra were recorded at 4 cm^{-1} resolution from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} for 20 scans of each sample.
X-Ray diffraction (WAXS)	WAXS analysis was performed by an X-ray diffractometer (Bruker, D8 Advance) operated at 40 kV with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54\text{ \AA}$) using a Lynx Eye detector.
High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM)	(HR-TEM) was performed by a (JEOL 2010EX) instrument with an accelerated voltage of 200 kV.
Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)	Thermomechanical properties of the nanocomposites was performed using a DMA instrument (TA Instruments, model Q-800) at a constant frequency (1 Hz) with a static force of 0.02 N from -100 to 150°C at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.
Tensile tests	Tensile tests of the films of uniform thickness were carried out using a universal testing machine (Zwick Roell, Z005) at a strain rate of 1 mm/min at room temperature.
Dielectric properties	Dielectric properties of the nanocomposite films were measured by using a Solartron impedance analyzer (model 1260) at frequencies ranging from 10^2 to 10^7 Hz with an oscillation voltage of 100 mV.

Fig. 2. TEM image of (a) GLF1, (b) RPF3, (c) GPF5 and (d) MPF10.

from the infrared absorption bands at 764 cm^{-1} and 840 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the α - and β -phases of PVDF, respectively. G-g-PANI/PVDF nanocomposite with 5 wt% filler shows highest amount of beta phase (91%). Calculation following the above equation we have got 90% β -polymorph in RPF5 and 86% β -polymorph in case of MPF10.

β -phase formation of PVDF in the composite films is also supported from WAXS pattern shown in Fig. 3b. The diffrac-

tion peaks at 17.7° , 18.4° , 19.9° and 26.7° of neat PVDF correspond to (100), (020), (110) and (021) reflections of α -phase¹¹. With gradual increase of G-g-PANI in GPF composite the α -phase peaks intensity decreases and at 5 wt% filler only one peak is observed at 20.7° corresponding to (110/200) Miller planes of β -phase crystal of PVDF¹⁷. PANI functionalized graphene provides stronger dipole-dipole interaction between -CONH bonds of G-g-PANI with the $>\text{CF}_2$ dipoles of PVDF and ion-dipole interaction between N^+ of PANI with $>\text{CF}_2$ dipoles of bulk PVDF. Thus WAXS also supports a major β -phase formation in case of GLF3, RPF5 and MPF10.

Mechanical properties:

The stress-strain measurement is used to determine the increment of mechanical properties of the GLF and RPF composite films (Fig. 4), as an example. PVDF shows an ultimate stress of 10 MPa but at 3 wt% GO-IL in PVDF (GLF3) it has the value 72 MPa. On the other hand RPF5 shows maximum stress of 46 MPa. The increase of stress value is because of the interaction of functionalized 2D nanomaterials with the bulk PVDF matrix. But we observe a small increase of ultimate strain value for RPF5 composite and decrease of ultimate strain value for GLF3 (Table 2).

Dynamic mechanical property of the nanocomposites (GLF and RPF) are also measured. Storage modulus (G') indicates the ability of the material to store energy and G''

Fig. 3. (a) FTIR and (b) WAXS of PVDF and the nanocomposites.

Fig. 4. Stress vs strain curve for PVDF, GLF3 and RPF5 composites.

Table 2. Stress, strain, storage modulus, dc-conductivity of PVDF, GLF3, RPF5, GPF5 and MPF10

Composite name	Stress (MPa)	Strain (%)	Storage modulus (G') (MPa) at 25°C	dc-conductivity (S/cm)
PVDF	10	9.5	1468	4.6×10^{-13}
GLF3	72	4.47	2440	8.9×10^{-3}
RPF5	46	17.6	2350	7×10^{-3}
GPF5	–	–	–	3.18×10^{-5}
MPF10	–	–	–	6.2×10^{-8}

value of the composites are presented in Table 2. G' value of PVDF is 1468 MPa but GLF3 and RPF5 show the value of 2440, 2350 MPa respectively at 25°C. The enhancement of G' is because of the synergistic effect of functionalized 2D

nanomaterials having high large surface area, homogeneous dispersion and strong interfacial adhesion in the PVDF matrix¹⁸.

dc-conductivity:

PVDF is an electrically insulating material having low dc-conductivity of 5.4×10^{-13} S/cm. But dc-conductivity of the composites increases shown in Table 2. In each composite there is an increase of conductivity by 5–6 orders showing a maximum of 8.9×10^{-3} S/cm for GLF3. This higher value of dc-conductivity may be attributed to the good interfacial adhesion of fillers and formation of 3D network with in PVDF matrix¹⁸.

Dielectric properties:

The dielectric constant (ϵ') of PVDF and different composite samples are measured with the variation of frequency at 30°C, shown in Fig. 5a. The dielectric constant values decrease with increasing frequency for all the samples. The decrease of dielectric constant value is related to the failure of dipoles to rotate quickly leading to a lag between the frequency of oscillating dipole and the applied field¹⁹. For all the nanocomposites dielectric value increases with increasing filler content at a constant frequency of 100 Hz. The increase of dielectric constant can be explained by the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars interfacial polarization for the different conductive fillers²⁰. Homogeneous dispersion and interaction of the nanofillers in PVDF matrix is mainly responsible for the increase of dielectric constant. Two neighbouring con-

Fig. 5. (a) Variation of dielectric constant of different nanocomposites with frequency and (b) dielectric constant of nanocomposites at 100 Hz at 30°C.

ducting layers of nanofillers can be imagined as electrodes of the nanocapacitor and the insulating PVDF layer in between act as nanodielectric, thus producing microcapacitor network²⁰. The synergistic effects of functionalized 2D nanomaterials increases the interaction with PVDF enhancing the dispersion resulting an increase of dielectric constant. GLF3, RPF5, GPF5, MPF10 exhibit dielectric constant of 13.5, 446, 264 and 586 at 100 Hz at room temperature (Fig. 5b). Interaction of functionalized 2D nanofillers with the >CF₂ dipoles of PVDF improves compatibility as well as the dielectric properties of the nanocomposites.

Conclusions

Homogeneously dispersed functionalized 2D nanofillers nanocomposites with PVDF were prepared which shows improvement of piezoelectric beta polymorph and dielectric constant compare to bulk polymer. Maximum beta polymorph formation occurs at G-g-PANI/PVDF with 5 wt% filler. MoS₂-PANI/PVDF nanocomposite shows highest dielectric constant of 586 at 100 Hz with 10 wt% of that nanocomposite. We believe that these functionalized 2D nanofiller/PVDF composites with significant polar beta phase and dielectric constant could be used in future technological applications.

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